

UNDERSTANDING THE NEW GENERATION & THEIR CHOICES: PASSING THROUGH IDENTITY, FLEXIBILITY & MIGRATION CRISISⁱ

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Abstract:

Children are becoming the focus of the information age. How they develop their values and how strong their decisions are always questioned. The complex nature of the communication techniques and strategies of today and the multilingual, multicultural, multidimensional structure of the society force children to develop in a rather different way than before. With the impact of the media and the local, national, global values sometimes contradicting with another, it is rather interesting to see how the concepts are shaped and how the decision making processes are effected by the media in childhood and we should question the way they change. The decision making process and the importance of the media impact on it will illuminate how the communities will be governed in future which will also bring new perspectives regarding the environmental problems and social conflicts. The potential roles of children for the future and their understanding of equality, power and empowerment issues will give us a chance to understand the world dynamics of the future. This study aims to investigate the identity and reflection of the identity issues starting from the early ages of childhood, focusing more on the empowerment strategies, decision making process and managerial skills of children. Do we really know about the past or who really cares about the future? Why people would like to stick to the values or memories instead of starting life from the very beginning just like a child. Expecting for something concrete and something absolute would cause the brain to work in different ways. Even if we care much more about the children and provide almost everything they might need, the current generation and the past generation has a gap in between due to the valuing things in different ways. For those who suffered in their childhood, it seems to be too late to make sacrifices for the others throughout the rest of their lives since people have already closed their doors for differences or understanding. The paper would be questioning the media perspective

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and how media played an important role in their development and evolving process. What are the media and schooling expectations of these youngsters or how media shaped these expectations? What values have changed for them and who gave them the new ones? What are the flexible parts of their identity and how they make use of it to overcome the migration crisis? This unique study concentrates on the individual stories of 70 children in İstanbul passing through the identity and migration crisis at their early ages. Due to the limitations of the study and the ethical issues considered, the direct questions were never asked to them instead providing them the game like situations is preferred. These simulations were aimed to assess their aptitude and attitudes for values of the past, present and future. Rather than the quantitative one, this study aims to concentrate on the qualitative approach, focusing more on the tête-à-tête data collection techniques, face to face interviews and focus group works.

Keywords: migration generation, z generation, identity, media

Özet:

Çocuklar bilgi çağının odağı haline gelmiş durumdadır. Çocukların değerlerini nasıl geliştirdikleri ve kararlarının gücü de her zaman sorgulanmaktadır. Günümüz iletişim tekniklerinin ve stratejilerinin karmaşık doğası ve toplumun çok dilli, çok kültürlü, çok kültürlü yapısı çocukları eskiye oranla daha farklı bir şekilde gelişmeye zorlamaktadır. Medyanın olduğu kadar, yerel, ulusal, küresel değerlerin bazen bir başkasıyla çelişen etkisi ile, kavramların nasıl şekillendiğini ve karar alma süreçlerinin medya tarafından çocuklukta nasıl etkilendiğini görmek oldukça ilginç sonuçlar ortaya çıkarmaktadır. Bu da değerlerin, söylemin, karar verme süreçlerinin çocukluktan başlayarak nasıl şekillendiği ile ilgili önemli ipuçları ortaya koymakta ve değişimlerin yönünün, doğasının saptanması gerekliliğini gündeme getirmektedir. Çocukların söylemleri, gelecekte toplumların nasıl yönetileceğini ve çevresel problemler ve sosyal çatışmalarla ilgili yeni bakış açıları getireceklerini aydınlatacaktır. Çocukların gelecek için öngördükleri roller ve eşitlik, güç ve güçlendirme konuları hakkındaki farkındalıklarının gelişmesi, bize geleceğin dünya dinamiklerini anlama şansı verecektir. Bu çalışma, çocukluğun erken yaşlarından başlayarak kimlik sorunlarının kimliğini ve yansımaları araştırmayı, güçlendirme stratejileri, karar alma süreci ve çocukların yönetim becerilerine odaklanmayı amaçlamaktadır. Geçmiş gerçekten biliyor muyuz veya geleceği gerçekten önemsiyor muyuz? Neden insanlar, bir çocuk gibi en baştan yaşama başlamak yerine değerlere veya anılara bağlı kalmak isterler. Somut ve mutlak bir şey beklemek beynin farklı şekillerde çalışmasına neden olur. Çocukları çok daha fazla önemsesek ve ihtiyaç duyabilecekleri hemen hemen her şeyi sağlasak bile, şimdiki nesil ile geçmiş nesiller arasında şeylerin farklı şekillerde değerlendirilmesi nedeniyle bir boşluk oluşmaktadır. Çocukluklarında acı çekenler için, yaşamları boyunca diğerleri için fedakarlık yapmak için çok zor görünüyor, çünkü insanların çoğu zaten farklılıklara ya da anlayışa, hoşgörüyü kapılarını kapatmış durumdadır. Bu çalışma, medya perspektifini ve medyanın gelişim ve gelişim sürecinde çocukların kimlikleri hakkında karar alma

konusunda nasıl önemli bir rol oynadığını sorgulamaktadır. Bu gençlerin medya ve okul beklentilerinin neler olduğunu veya medyanın bu beklentileri nasıl şekillendirdiğini, onlar için hangi değerlerin değiştiğini ve yenilerini kimlerin verdiğini araştırmaktadır. Kimliğinin esnek parçalarının neler olduğunu ve göç kaynaklı bu krizi yenmek için onu nasıl kullandıklarını sorgulamaktadır. Bu çalışma bir yandan erken yaşta kimlik ve göç krizinden geçen İstanbul'daki 70 çocuğun bireysel hikayelerine odaklanırken, bir diğer yandan daha önce yapılan benzer çalışmalarla sonuçlarını karşılaştırmaktadır. Çalışmanın kısıtlamaları ve göz önünde bulundurulmuş etik konular nedeniyle, çocuklara hiçbir zaman doğrudan sorular sorulmamış, onlara oyun benzeri durumlar sunulması ve bunlar üzerinde konuşulması tercih edilmiştir. Bu simülasyonlar geçmiş, şimdiki ve gelecekteki değerler için yeteneklerini ve tutumlarını değerlendirmeyi amaçlamaktadır. Nicel olduğu kadar nitel yaklaşıma da odaklanmayı amaçlayan bu çalışma, veri toplama teknikleri bağlamında, yüz yüze görüşmeler ve odak grup çalışmalarına odaklanmıştır.

Anahtar Sözcükler: göç nesli, z nesli, kimlik, medya

1. Introduction

It's not only the adults but also the children who care about the identity problems and future expectations. Especially, when the immigration circumstances are considered, the life crumbles all of a sudden and leave people helpless and abandoned in some corner of the world. Apart from the dystopia, the future expectations give more motivation to the new life span of the individuals.

We expect to understand the new generation, their way of thinking, their choices and their problems. However, passing through the identity crises could be very difficult even for the children in normal lives. When we put the problems of mobility, war conditions as well as the migration crisis the limits of childhood become different. Planning for life is a crucial need, however, in wartime conditions, no planning works in the realities of a problematic world. People start planning for future at the early ages while the circumstances play an important role on the details of the projected future. However the brain keeps on developing up to the age of 21 whereas the healthy decisions are expected to be given after this maturation period.

To Eccles (1999), the development of children ages 6 to 14 are too important. These years are called as the middle childhood and early adolescence and believed to be a time of important developmental advances that establish children's sense of identity. Eccles puts forward that during these years, children make strides toward adulthood by becoming competent, independent, self-aware, and involved in the world beyond their families. Biological and cognitive changes transform children's bodies and minds.

Social relationships and roles change dramatically as children enter school, join programs, and become involved with peers and adults outside their families. During middle childhood, children develop a sense of self-esteem and individuality, comparing

themselves with their peers. They come to expect they will succeed or fail at different tasks.

Of course the tasks and types would be differing from one culture to another as well as from one generation to another. In the past the children could only expect to become teachers, doctors or engineers because these were the most important and prestigious occupations of those times. However, the children of the modern society expect to become something that their parents never heard before.

Planning for the future starts as early as research puts forward that (Beach & Mitchell, 1987) the descriptive theory of decision making depends on the fact that decision makers represent information as images. They differentiate four types of images. One image consists of principles that recommend pursuit of specific goals. This mainly does not apply for the kids living in the refugee camps, since their specific goals might only be short term ones regarding their mobility in a war space. In the case of children of war, these kids could never have specific goals of their own except to struggle to be alive. These type of future planning requires some kind of dwelling on the goal, concentrating on it and putting the self into the shoes of the future self, some kind of future projection. However, in war time the children do not have such a luxury as to make it happen.

Images could be permanent or temporary. Yet, in childhood, most of the images are temporary since the child's concentration wouldn't be lasting so long. That's why a second image representing the future state of events that would result from attainment of those goals would be the one even a step further than the previous one. A third image consists of the plans that are being implemented in the attempt to attain the goals. A fourth image represents the anticipated results of the plans. Yet, being a refugee, the child seems to have no time for pleasant memories, future planning or permanent decisions since nothing is stable for them.

For example, if a child has a happy family and close school, nice friends and healthy nutrition, only then s/he may think of becoming successful or having a better homework next time. That means stability and maintenance are very important for identity development and future perceptions.

Out of the 2.3 million refugees living in Turkey since the beginning of Syrian war, most of the population is suffering due to the unexpected results of changes. It's not only the mobility of the population or people it's also the mobility of the facts, feelings, thinking and evaluating styles, education tendencies, future expectations. Being a refugee in any country sounds like swimming in an ocean. Your feet never feel the soil that means you have a loss of trust and confidence and day by day, you lose the sense of feeling and belonging.

Out of the 2.3 million refugees most of them are children. Even if the ones having a tent in the camps have far better facilities for those whose families have chosen to live outside the camp the life could be worse. While most of the kids join the schools in the camps, these children living here and there in a risky world seem to be missing education. On one hand the educational point of view regarding the refugee's situation, currently, is becoming more and more complex. On the other hand, one of the most important

issues, education is still regarded as the only way to fight the disabilities and uncomfortable situation that the war brings up. Most of the kids coming from Syria were under the effect of war for more than four or five years due to the constant fear and threats in the fields. Before their arrival to the foreign lands they were also mobile in their own territories. Even if the psychological support is provided for the campers, these kids in the street, seem to be lost at all and constitute the riskiest as the unlucky part. Now not only the insufficient substructure, lack of facilities and financial sources make it difficult for them to continue their education but also the fear deep inside their hearts make it difficult for them to believe in that education is somewhat positive to make their lives better. Instead they tend to perceive education as a kind of alienation and it is difficult for them to get back to their rows as students and get ready to learn, concentrate and motivate themselves as if nothing had happened. The situation is somewhat gloomy for those who are handicapped or requiring special education with learning disabilities.

However, not all the kids are miserable or detached from their identity or future planning. In certain aspects, we see that Syrian kids are given the utmost importance, equipped with the best materials, provided better established schools with bilingual and skillful teachers. Some even have more teachers to teach them Arabic and Turkish and perhaps other languages. With all these positive sides these kids are the candidates to become the future leaders. Sometimes, these are the kids who already participated good schools in Syria and still have the opportunities to join a special school in Turkey. Apart from their mother tongue Arabic, knowing Russian, French and English before, now they practice to learn Turkish and even Japanese. The advantageous classes provide them better opportunities empowering these refugee kids for a better future. The difficulties they pass through only flourished their skills to communicate even better and in crises situations. Language means a lot to them to mean themselves under all conditions.

There are many studies arguing that exposure to a second or third language at early ages, especially at a pre-literate stage may improve metalinguistic skills, in particular, speech-sound awareness, which is implicated in reading mastery, benefits from this support (Campbell, 1995). Just in recent years, scientists have begun to show that the advantages of bilingualism are even more fundamental than being able to converse with a wider range of people. According to the research, bilingual kids seem to be smarter than the monolingual ones.

Bilingualism, might have a profound effect on the brain, improving cognitive skills not related to language and even shielding against dementia in old age (Bhattacharjee, 2012; Petitto, & Dunbar, 2004) But not all are lucky. Sometimes, it might be the nature of childhood that individuals see the details more than the general view or concentrate more on the negativities rather than the positive sides of the life. Yet, knowing the language may not be enough to talk about their fears and hopes.

Throughout the way, living so many difficulties, these children usually seem to be silent compared to the others

2. The Aim and Methodology

The paper would be questioning the media perspective and how media played an important role in the development and evolving process of the children. Regarding questions such as 'What are the media and schooling expectations of these youngsters or how media shaped these expectations?', 'What values have changed for them and who gave them the new ones?', 'What are the flexible parts of their identity and how they make use of it to overcome the migration crisis?' the paper provides the findings in the form of statistics.

This paper concentrates on the individual stories of 70 children in İstanbul passing through the identity and migration crisis at their early ages. Due to the limitations of the study and the ethical issues considered, the direct questions were never asked to them. Instead game like situations is preferred to collect the data from these sample groups. These simulations were aimed to assess their aptitude and attitudes for values of the past, present and future. As well as a quantitative one, this study aims to concentrate more on a qualitative approach, focusing more on the tete-a-tete data collection techniques, face to face interviews and focus group works mainly based on the oral reflections of the participants. Thus, sometimes not all the children were asked the same questions but the overall findings is summarized.

3. Findings and Interpretations

Being a Syrian Child in Turkey is a very complex issue. Being a Turkish Child in Turkey is becoming even more complex. Having a healthy childhood somewhere in the World seems to be almost impossible in nowadays. There are obvious differences between the kids arriving to Turkey just before the war and arriving during the war bag and baggage. There is also a definite difference between the kids living in the campsite, providing free schooling, food and shelter and the kids living in the tents outside the camps or as kids apart from their families.

Children living in the campsite, happy in general but mainly feel uneasy when they have foreigners or strangers around. Even if these people seem to be from the same culture 92% of them do not feel themselves confident enough within their shelters and circumstances. Yet, 56% of them still state that they do not feel themselves in a confident situation even with their families.

4. Source of Information and Media

Even if they are aware of the fact that there might be different values and languages around 89% of them state that they wouldn't like to live in such circumstances. A very tiny amount of the participants, 5,6% state that they are afraid of people speaking another language. 97% of these kids do not have any tendency to learn more about the other

cultures. Thus, the percentage of xenophobia seems to be too high among these children or they are indifferent to their surroundings.

Most of the kids under 3 never realize that they are in a foreign country or sometimes in war situation. They are only aware of the fact that they are constantly mobile and this increases their feelings of insecurity that makes them cry in general. The ones who realize that they are in abroad, don't want to stay here long with the hope of getting back soon. These are mainly the kids dwelling upon the information they get from their family surroundings since their language or skills are not improved enough to help them to get the information on their own. Still even these youngsters have an access to the media and war scenes frequently.

As for the elder kids, the more the multilayered communication skills improve, the more independent they become. Thus, their source of information turns to be the media, internet and peers instead of the closer family members. The ones who are aware of the multicultural circumstances follow the media in their mother tongue or they develop certain strategies to understand the paralinguistic features. Media occupies a lot of time if the kids are not attending to school or extracurricular activities in the camp side. Moreover, sometimes, it's not the main choice of the child but rather an exposure to the adult's media since the news cover an important place in the lives of the refugees. 98% interview participants believe that they do not have any right to choose their media. However they mainly make use of their own media via satellites or online connections. The ones in the campsite had an access to the multimedia and computer games. The digital world seem to be the only thing that makes them happy.

When they're attending to school it's interesting for them to experience team teaching in their classes, one teacher is teaching in Arabic and one in Turkish. Within the cultural, technological, educational and socio-economic conditions they are in, some of them are even bilingual or had a good education in the past. These kids seem to be involved more with the society and make better use of the media. Sometimes they even help and guide the others with the customs or language. They help them to make the others understand their culture better or they translate the things and perform the function of a bridge between their society and the others. They tend to be the leaders of the present and future. They make good use of media and try to catch up with the news, etc. to add to their discourse. They even provide minute details to elaborate their speech to feel more competent in the field.

5. Understanding The New Generation

Understanding the new generation is not easy even in normal circumstances. Under the war circumstances it's even more difficult. With the impact of the modern communication styles and technology, the generation gap is evolving and getting deeper. In the context of family communication, in the context of peer cooperation and fulfilling the community responsibilities and other type of actions.

Remembering another study with the kids in 2004 it's obvious to see the fears of children: They believe that all the problems of the world are actually planted by adults. In 2004, according to the results of a survey of 664 children and 4 schools, (Görpe & Pembecioğlu, 2005) many of them were found to have fears regarding their loneliness, disappearance, abduction, fear of unknown people and having a deep disappointment in life as well as a deep suspicion to be hurt by someone they love or trust, fear of losing their trust, falling from their eyes and fear of losing their love are the most prominent ones. Death, punishment, lie and slander, fear of being underestimated and failing are also the basic fears of children. Fear of violence, see people fighting disputes, natural disasters, accidents are also a separate type of fear. They were more afraid of being excluded by their friends than being hungry if they are mocked with their feelings. 12% of the children suffer from general unhappiness and it is seen that they have put forward all kinds of excuses to be unhappy due to the depth of their injuries in the past. It was very likely that these children will be developing bad habits and suicidal tendencies in the future or violent actions and rudeness towards the others. Mainly they tend to refuse to understand the others and to be understood by the others. Usually, people having an experience of natural disasters, wars or accidents also develop a separate type of fear. They do not want to lose their connection with their friends. They do not want to be misunderstood or injured with their feelings. The fear of exclusion is more than anything else under these circumstance. The feeling of safety as well as trust are crucial for them. The reason of mentioning a dated back research here is just make sure that their feelings were much similar to those of the interviewed refugee children. That means, it might be somewhat normal to feel like at those ages even if there is no war around.

The risk group mainly involves the kids who were left alone or lost their parents, family members, without having any support from the surrounding group members, involving both the younger and/or the older ones sharing similar experiences with them. However, the research also had findings to make us see that children might not be happy even if they live with their parents. The sample group was consisting of 210 Turkish students, yet, the percentage of the ones feeling themselves content and happy with their families are only 46%.

It is surprising to see that within the overall group 5% of them believe that they do not have even peace at home. 8% of the children between the ages of 14-16 never ever believe that Peace is possible. Some of them state that 'The elders never pave the way for peace' they say and even declare that 'They are afraid of each other that's why they need to have war.' Sometimes, they blame the family members accusing them to be a part of the opposition party, rebellious ones or being on the side of the government, etc. Thus, they lose their trust even for the ones who are the part of the family. This might be stemming from the conversation they eavesdrop through the other family members or due to the reflections of their peers and even their families. Once there is an accused one in the family, the hopes and trust of that child is lost sometimes for a life time.

Out of the whole sample 69.2% presents a dystopic point of view for the present and future. Some of them believe that there is peace in the world but not in their own

country. The ones believing that European Countries have peace and freedom reach only 20%. There was a group of 18 % believing that peace is in other countries such as USA, Norway, and Sweden. Mostly they believe that peace is somewhere out there in isolated places where nobody lives. Sometimes they state that, there is some inner peace in their heart when they are in Turkey, so that they do not need to go to any other country. Around 10% claim to be remembering themselves in Turkey in the past due to the kinship and relatives being in the country. Thus, they tend to develop a kind of belongingness to the country.

A general misery rate is around 12% of children. These kids are under the risk because sometimes they just give up or feel themselves not that much valuable. They feel unloved, neglected or even hated. They seem to have no bounds in life and feeling more and more alienated to themselves, to their surroundings, people and society. Few of them reflect disobedience behaviors, but mostly they are in the mood of silence but introverted. In future these children might have a negative tendency of bad habits or suicide. Their psychology is not related with the mobility they experienced or the lack of motivation, material needs, etc. yet, they seem to be in a deep shock. Even if their parents are caring enough, these kids have a problem inside and they tend to think of death at least once every day and sometimes have pseudo suicides in their dreams just to imagine what would happen when it really happens. They feel neglected and underestimated, they do not have any confidence to themselves and to the others. These are usually the ones experiencing deep traumas, deaths and losses in their life. They have a great tendency to degrade and undervalue themselves feeling unworthy.

6. Their Choices Passing Through Identity, Flexibility & Migration Crisis

The study conducted by Development of Social and Cultural Life Association (SKYGD) was a field study conducted in order to examine the life conditions, expectations and problems of Syrian children living in Turkey. For this study 100 children living in various districts of Istanbul had been interviewed and their reflections of "Being refugee children in Turkey" is questioned. Most of the kids were attending to the schools. In this case either we may call it the impact of education or the stereotyped reflections in the society, they really put education into the core of their lives. That's why the report unveils that the most fundamental demand of these children is to continue their education, which they are deprived of for some time due to the financial and other problems.

Keeping in mind that the majority of Syrian refugees are children, puts the question of future projections into a very important point. It's not only the individual impact but also the social and international impact that we should be questioning since their expectations, decisions and actions would be structuring the future. However having about 2.5 million children are having difficulties in accessing basic services like education, healthcare and sheltering make it difficult to have better expectations for future. According to the data of Turkish Ministry of Interior General Directorate of Migration Management, 922.000 Syrian children live in Turkey at the moment. It is

estimated that 622.000 of them cannot take part education. Conducting studies with children and young people for 2 years, SKYGD released the conclusions of the field study consisting of interviews with 100 Syrian children. Speaking to the children between the ages of 7 and 16 the Association notes that children older than 12 cannot be interviewed easily because majority of them are working already in part time or full time jobs. Some also refuse to be interviewed.

The children interviewed for this research were mainly living out of the camps, in tents. They were asked where they were living in Syria and how they came to Turkey. Even if some kids argue that it is still Syria, without noticing that they are in a different country, 95% of the sample group families came to Istanbul from Aleppo, Damascus and Qamishlo. Some admitted that on the way, they were looking for the enemies and found out the Turks and couldn't believe that these people are their enemies because they were so nice. One other finding is that the children arriving after 2013 weren't accepted to the camps. On the other hand, the ones who stayed in a camp don't have very pleasant memories. One of them said: *"We came to Karkamış camp and stayed there for two months. It was so bad that we returned to Syria. Then we ran away again due to the war and came to Antep."*

According to Kazazⁱⁱⁱ, another point emphasized in the report is the fact that the children cannot access basic services like education and healthcare sufficiently. If a father or specifically mother is missing, they cannot be placed in the camps. In Turkey, Syrian refugees must be registered in order to receive such services, yet 23% children stated that they don't have any kind of ID. Only 31% of the children said that they receive healthcare service from official institutions.

Out of all the sample 38% of the children go to school and 39% children are almost illiterate. Girls have more difficulty in going to school due to their responsibilities at home such as to take care of the younger sisters /brothers. Even if they are in a different community, a great majority of children state that they want to go to school and consider education as a way to freedom. The reasons why they cannot go to school vary from working for the family to financial problems. Sometimes school is the only environment for the kids to feel that they are still children. It's also the only place to provide them freedom to be of their own and to become individuals rather than only being a part of a greater community. At school, they are mainly cooperative, happy and interactive.

When the children's relations with their environment is assessed, some children stated that there are people helping and treating them nicely in their neighborhood and some others state that both adults and children are treating them badly. 41% of the children state that they don't have any friends neither in the neighborhood nor at school. Some children state that *"I haven't had any friends for the last two years"* or *"I miss my friends in Aleppo"* or *"My best friend died and now I don't have a friend anymore"*. Discrimination and violence are important factors and they stand on the way to establish a healthy friendship. A child says, *"When I get the ball, other children take it away from me and throw it under a car."* Mostly, the kids are so silent that they never answer you back if you do not insist on getting an answer.

ⁱⁱⁱ <http://www.agos.com.tr/en/article/16525/being-a-syrian-child-in-turkey>

Children were also asked what they think about Turkey. While 71% of them state that they hadn't knew anything about Turkey before coming here, 80% of them stated that they wouldn't like to be here if there wasn't a war in their country. Only 7% of the children stated that they don't want to get back to Syria, because they think that there is nothing left to return to. Their expectations from Turkey is to have better life standards: better houses, job opportunities, education and healthcare. However, there are also children stating that they don't have any expectations. These kids seem to be hopeless feeling themselves perhaps excluded from the society even if all their needs were fulfilled. Regarding their future occupation they seem to be as traditional as the generation of a few decades ago. 36% of them want to become doctors and 36% of them want to become teachers. Remembering that these occupations refer to serving to the masses and communities and this gives us the degree how vulnerable and fragile they are in fact. That means the really care about civic services and citizenship issues. Most of them stated that they are ready to act voluntarily. And many of them admitted that they already helped the other people in an altruistic way.

Figure 1: Age of the Sample Group

For the sample group, alongside with this quantitative approach, a qualitative approach is also followed and the kids had a face to face interview as well as a focus group discussion. During the interview the children introduced themselves with a few sentences and had a picture drawing session and discussed the past, present and future expectations. During these interviews, most of them put themselves in a transparent way as to give us clues about their inner selves. So that we might have an insight on their situation.

Regarding the interview group, 68% of the participants were girls and 32% of them were boys. Most of the participants had a huge impact of the war on their little shoulders. 63% of them lost their parents or relatives in war. Some of them have deep traumas and that's why only 16% of them have a future perspective in their expectations. They still cannot understand why they are here in Turkey, why this war is happening, etc. In other words, they are still stick to the past and there seems to be no way for them to have a future before solving the problems in the past. The rest of the group 84% mostly deal with

the present situation rather than the future. 37% of them who don't have any loss and who have a close contact with their peers, have a kind of fear inside that they feel the necessity of stating that they did not lose anybody else in the war but they suffered a lot. They sometimes feel themselves guilty or awkward in such a situation that they are happier than the others.

Unfortunately only 16% of these kids were positive about the future, yet a great majority, around 84% of them seem to be no future expectations. Yet, most of the kids, apparently 69% of them have a decided occupation at the moment. The impact of war on children is so obvious that 80% of them state the words "war" several times in their discourse.

7. Conclusion

The kids are fragile and they don't think of themselves in an egoistic way, instead they mainly concentrate the needs of the family, little brothers or sisters and the other peers they have close contact. 41% of them live with large families having at least two or more brothers / sisters up to seven.

Some of them have 6 or seven other children in their family. That means they lack most of the necessary space, interest and stuff for a more personalized life. In a way they are forced to live in the form of a community and they need to stay in their community. When it becomes a way of life, they have a deep fear in their heart to make up their own decisions or actions.

That means the media, the money, the requirements are all shared within the family and they have not much chance to feel themselves as a person. How can we expect them to develop a healthy identity living in the campsite for 5 years or more? 59% of the kids live in smaller families what we call a nuclear family without any other children. Yet, this does not mean that they gather all the interest, time and revenue of the family. Mainly that means they have elder people at home to be looked after.

7.1 Education Problem

Considering the problem on the side of the education platform Özer & Ateşok, (2016) state that an analysis of the legislation and the transformation of public policy for the training of Syrian kids under Turkey's temporary protection provided benefits and better services rather than sufferings.

The more the parents get better jobs and higher standards, the better the kids perform at schools. Thus, it could be important to note that more than 15.000 Syrians were trained to get qualified and were placed into permanent jobs out of the camps. And while 300.000 Syrians are in temporary stations in the camps but the ratio of the Syrians outside the camps reach to three million (Özer & Ateşok, 2016).

These temporary education centers planned not as a long-term public policies but with short and medium term solutions to satisfy the immediate needs. It is clear that these temporary education centers are left out of the system entirely due to the urgency of the

situation. Yet, the government is taking measures of urgency based on the geographical and local needs. Thus, the Syrian children will be cared for their short-term and medium-term and long term solutions. One of the main goals is to achieve as high enrollment rates as possible since these fall dramatically both in Syria and in Turkey. Yet, not only the governmental bodies but also the national and international NGOs seem to be supporting some good quality and bilingual schools as well as providing precautions for the drop of rates. As the governmental bodies spend as much as 12 billion dollars for the refugees up to the time, the NGOs as well contributed almost an equal share to satisfy the needs of the refugees. However, these short term solutions need to turn to be the long term ones considering all the possible solutions (Özer & Ateşok, 2016).

According to the European Union definition of deprivation in 2016, approximately one in every three children in Turkey, in other words, 7 million 510 thousand children live in households suffering severe material deprivation. Between 2015 and 2016, great increases in the deprivation rates of children observed specifically in Western Anatolia, Istanbul, Central Anatolia, Eastern Black Sea and the Mediterranean regions. Mainly the increase is caused by the fact that they lack heating and cannot cover the basic nutritional needs or unexpected expenditures. 47% of the children in Southeast Anatolia, 37.3% in the Middle East and 36% in the Mediterranean are not warm enough during the cold season. With these figures it seems that the proportion of children living in severe material deprivation in Turkey lags behind all European Union countries.

7.2 Material Deprivation

The measure of material deprivation is one of the methods used to measure and analyze the poverty level of countries. This method is considered as an approach that sheds light on the general level of poverty of the country since it includes evaluations of living standards of surveyed dwellings. Long-suffering poverty, a consequence of poverty, is a temporary deprivation in adulthood, which in children usually lasts forever and carries the risk of being passed on to future generations.

Remembering the study of Darbaz, & Kolaşin (2009) we know that there were 125.000 Turkish kids not attending to school and 30.000 of them never have been to school, these Syrian kids seem to have a great chance to be able to attend to schools even if they are all in a war situation. Yet, since they all live in the campsites or in somewhat sheltered areas, they benefit from the free schooling systems provided for the refugees. One other thing is that as Dinçer & Kolaşin (2008) figured out, Turkey is losing the younger generation. 17% of the young people are unemployed. Even if they are employed, the working conditions are harsh for them. Once decided on working, the law forces them to work as a full time worker not permitting to go to school. So, they have to decide if they need education or Money. That's why, in this age group, 1.6 million (50%) of the men in this age group, and 1.9 million (61%) of the girls, in other words a total of 3.5 million young people are not enrolled at schools.

Table 1: Children with Deprivation

Sub-items	Number of children (Thousands)	Ratio of children with deprivation (% , 2016)	Ratio of children with deprivation (% , 2015)	Ratio of children with deprivation (% , 2014)
Severe Deprivation of Material	7.510	38,0	36,4	36,2
Heating	5.554	28,1	20,0	19,1
Unexpected expenses	7.491	37,9	37,4	33,3
Nutrition	8.065	40,8	40,3	39,2
Holiday	13.983	70,7	75,8	74,6
Television	25	0,1	0,3	0,3
Washing machine	227	1,1	1,5	2,3
Car	9.585	48,4	50,5	53
Telephone	15	0,1	0,1	0,1
Rent and invoices	8.589	43,4	47,5	51,3

Source: TURKSTAT 2014, 2015 and 2016 Income and Living Conditions Survey - Severe child poverty according to sub-categories (2014-2016).

That means not only the Syrian children but also, perhaps more than that the Turkish children are in danger. According to the data while 1/3 of the children were suffering from severe financial deprivation in 2014 (Gürsel, Uysal & Kökkızıl, 2014), the ratio went up as to 1/2 of children suffering due to severe financial deprivation in 2015 (Gürsel, Uysal & Durmaz, 2015) and even higher in 2018.

Figure 3: Eurostat; 2013 – 2015 and 2016 Income and Living Conditions

Depending upon the geographical regions, the socio-economic factors might change. That's why when the geographical distribution is considered with its 17 million population, İstanbul as the largest metropolitan of Europe is even at the threshold level considering the Income and Living Conditions survey. It seems that the numbers get higher regarding the areas where Syrian population is settled such as South-Eastern part of the country.

Figure 2: Different Parts of Turkey Having Different Rates
(Source: TURKSTAT 2016 Income and Living Conditions)

As a result, it would be a vogue attempt to disregard the physical, social and economic aspects of the country in order to concentrate on the Syrian kids and their identity, flexibility or migration crisis. The population living in the area is also suffering throughout the years.

7.3 The Means And Media

In most cases, the Syrians ones having access to multimedia devices in their schools, or washing machines, television sets and planned nutrition packs are the targets of the envious gazes. This gap brings out the collaboration with the Turkish and Syrian kids at school. Sometimes, kids look at the most luxurious cars are parked in front of the crooked tents or shanty towns in Adana or Gaziantep. Of course they cannot figure out that it's perhaps the only thing they have left in the hands of the migrating family. Some kids state that they had a better life in Syria, having more cars and two or more houses. Looking at the holes in their pants, this kind of a discourse has a very little chance to be convincing enough for a Turkish peer at school.

Even if they lack the basics the Syrian kids seem to be having the latest and the most expensive smart phones in their hands as to conduct their conversations with their family members far away. But, this seems to be luxurious for those who couldn't have any access to them. Furthermore, for these suffering from the rising rents in the area put

the blame on these new “guests” and had a negative attitude towards them just from the beginning. We know that the situation is somewhat complex.

7.4 Tailoring Individual And Social Futures Through The Invisible Impact Of War

Having the greatest wave of migration of the 21st century, Turkey is faced and in a way forced to welcome 3 million Syrians in the last five years. Witnessing the war and leaving the school during the running away and surviving activities, specifically the kids are in risk of developing necessary literacy skills for the contemporary generation. On one hand equipped with the technology and mobility of the latest applications and social media we have the Y generation in rows at school in Turkey and all over the world. On the other hand we also have a part of the Syrian generation missing education. Regarding the education system and rapidly changing curriculum designs, at the moment they seem to be unable to catch the current trend.

The paper concentrates on the refugee situation in Turkey nowadays reaching to 3 million people and having almost half of them as children under 18 years old. The educational point of view regarding the refugees situation, currently, is becoming more and more a complex and important issue since education is still regarded as the only way to fight the disabilities and uncomfortable situation as well as the traumas that the war brings up. Most of the kids coming from Syria were under the effect of war for more than five years due to the constant fear and threats in the fields. These include mostly the unlucky children population missing education both in their countries and in Turkey. Lacking the appropriate learning skills, researching motivations, experiencing the traumas of war and even losing their language and communication skills these kids seem to be handicapped from the very beginning. Added to the situation the identity problems and the future threats the possibilities seem to be very negative since now it is difficult for them to get back to their rows as students and get ready to learn as if nothing had happened. Even if they get back to education, they are faced to be humiliated at school or in the social circumstances so they become losers for the second time. Thus the situation seems to be somewhat gloomy.

Even if we have a lot of statistics, field study and interviews, we have very limited knowledge about these young people's interests, hopes fears and actions in local - national - global issues. Being exposed to the heavy load of negative impact of the media even if it's the only source of information for them, what could be their main concerns. In the twenty-first century, being a refugee is a problematic and vague concept. When the concept of refugee is presented as a 'problem', there are different economic, political and cultural points of view. The refugees considered as the main strangers in society and sometimes directly attributed values of a foreigner even if they might have older roots in the society. However, considering the Turkish case in fact The Syrians are not total strangers to the peoples of nearby cities such as Hatay, Iskenderun, Antakya, Samandağı, Yayladağı, Reyhanlı. Yet, once they get the label of refugees, all of them were considered to be distant and dangerous ones.

The perceptions are created not only by the physical surroundings but also with the media. Regarding this as a very sensitive the media also chooses to be highly diversified and diverse mixing the minimized and maximized point of views. In the last decade, more immigration occurred than in all periods of history. In 2013, the number of people forced to migrate was over 50 million. More than four million Syrian women, men and children had to leave their homeland and migrated to neighboring countries. Whereas one out of five people in Lebanon is Syrian, for Jordan it is one out of four. The cost of escaping from war to peace is severe. Thousands of people die when they try to go to "better" countries. However, still 86% of the world's immigrants live in 'developing countries' and experience difficult conditions. Apart from the difficult conditions they face and the trauma they experience, the struggle with exclusion, xenophobia and the state of being considered as redundant in the societies they try to cling to, add to the daily social, cultural and economic challenges of immigrants.

It is important to note that satisfying the needs of over a million settled children in urban education require a huge responsibility and multifaceted demands on the half of education. But, anything for the sake of children and young people pay it back with positive results. No doubt it's not only the responsibility of a host country, Turkey, or only the governmental bodies to provide a healthy educational process to shape a better future for all but it requires the attention of a broader geography and joint sensitivity for future, caring more for the youngsters and their needs, to build the environment to flourish trust.

Appendix: Part of The Interview Data

- Girl - Ilaf: *"I was born in 2005. We fled to Turkey together with my parents and brothers and sisters 4 years ago. I haven't lost any relatives in the war, but we were terrified by the sounds of bombs. Even though we were homesick, I'm happy and safe here. We are grateful to the people of Turkey. I can speak very fluent English. I want to be a teacher in the future."*
- Girl - Ula: *"I was born in Idlib in 2002. I am a student at the 7th class. Our house was targeted by bombs in Syria. We came here together with my parents and 3 brothers / sisters four years ago. I want to be a doctor."*
- Girl - Cudi: *"I was born in Homs I am 12 years old and a student at the 5th class. We came here 4 years ago. I live with my parents. My cousin was martyred at war, our house was burned down. I want to be a teacher in the future."*
- Boy: Muataz: *"I was born in Idlib. I am 9 years old. I've been living in a tent city for two years. My father died in a traffic accident in Syria before the war. We haven't lost any one in my family, our house is not damaged. I want to be a doctor."*
- Girl: Fatma: *"I am 12 years old. I came to Turkey, 2,5 years ago. I want to be a doctor. We had 2 houses in Syria, they were both devastated as a result of the bombings. I haven't lost any of my close relatives in the battle, but I miss my sister who got married and left for Germany."*

- Boy – Ömer: *“I was born in Idlib in 2004. Bad system caused deaths of Syrians and forced the survivors to flee. We lived happily until our homes were destroyed. My city was at the hands of the State and our home was next to the city hospital. Airplanes were dropping bombs next to our home. My mother was pregnant at that time and lost the baby due to her fears. We walked for hours over the mountains. Then they sent us to this camp. We thank to Turkish citizens. We pray to Allah for them, Allah bless you all, protect your country.”*
- Girl – Sahra: *“I was in Syria, I studied 1st class there, I lost my father in war and I was so sad. Then, myself, my mother and sisters came to Turkey. I continue my education and I am now at the 4th class. I want to be an optician in the future. I wish Allah to end the war in Syria. Because I missed Syria so much.”*
- Girl – Fatma: *“I am 8 years old. My family and I went out of Syria because of the war. War destroyed our city. We came to Turkey. We live at the camp in Nizip. I attend the school here.”*
- Boy – Hamzee: *“I came here from Damascus. I left my home town because of the war. I came to Turkey. Before that I was very happy with my friends at my school or at home. I love to draw because I dream when I draw.”*
- Boy – Ahmet: *“My name is Ahmet, I am from Idlib. I attend the 9th class. We came to Turkey because of ar. We stay in container. I used to love drawing very much... Before the war I was drawing landscapes, but when the war broke out, I started to draw war situations. I want to be a painter when I grow up. I’m going to draw big pictures.”*
- Boy – Muhammed: *“I am Syrian. I came here from Idlib. We were in very bad conditions and our situation was very tough. When we arrived in here, Turkey gave us everything and accepted us in a very good manner. We would like to thank Turkey for everything they did for us.”*
- Girl – Hedir: *“When the war broke out, my father said, we should go to Turkey. Then we went to the border and my sister was sick. Then we went into a camp and I registered in a school. I joined in a girls’ soccer team and a painting course. I love to draw pictures.”*
- Boy – Sermed: *“I am at the 7th class. I am 13 years old. I attend Nizip container town school I am a hardworking student. I like drawing, soccer playing and swimming as hobbies. I missed Syria so much. I will be a doctor and I will help needy people.”*
- Girl – Fedye: *“I am 9 years old. We were living in Idlib. As the war became more violent, our house was destroyed as a result of the attacks. We moved to another place. When the attacks intensified also there, we were forced to migrate to Turkey.”*
- Girl – İlhem: *“I am 10 years old. We were living in Aleppo. Our house collapsed because of the bombing when the conflicts started. My father stayed in Aleppo for Jihad. But sent us to Turkey. Then he wounded and also came to Turkey.”*
- Girl – Nur: *“I am 8 years old. This war took away my dreams, my childhood and my future. I hope I will return to my country one day and live a happy life. I thank Allah that we came into Turkey and found a happy environment. I go to school here. I have friends and I can live again my childhood. I am very happy now. I thank my Turkish brothers for making this environment possible for us.”*

- Girl – Imren: *“I am 10 years old. We were living in Idlib. When the bombings started. I lost my uncle, maternal uncle and nephews, among my close relatives. Our house was destroyed and we had no place to stay. We had to come to Turkey.”*
- Girl – Tesnim: *“I am 7 years old. We were living in Central Aleppo When the war broke out, I was 4 years old and we left Aleppo. We arrived in the border towns, then passed to Turkey.”*
- Girl – Safa: *“I am 9 years old. We were living in Damascus. Bassar Al Assad’s brother confiscated our house and threw us to the street. We moved far away from them. My grandfather’s house was bombed and destroyed. Then we moved to Turkey, whole family.”*
- Boy – Hemdan: *“I am 9 years old. We are Turkomans. Our hometown witnessed severe conflicts. My uncle was martyred in heavy fightings. Then we moved to Turkey. Thank god we are happy in Turkey.”*
- Girl – Abir: *“I am Abir Jindi. I was born in Latakia, Syria in 2002. My mother’s name is Ayşe. My father was martyred in the war. We are 4 brothers and sisters. I attend 8th class. We came to Turkey because of the war in Syria.”*
- Boy – Ahmet: *“I am 10 years old Bassar Ah Assad was bombing us when we were in Syria. My father’s fingers were cut off and some people’s hands and feet were also cut, some were martyred. Some people’s houses were burned down. Women and children were crying and men were fighting. All the women and children were running towards the border. A child was running towards the border as if running to his mother. Then our camps were set up. I thank to Turkey.”*
- Girl – Aya: *“I am 14 years old I am a student at the 8th class. We are 7 brothers/sisters. We’ve come to Turkey from the city of Latakia, Syria since we were not safe in battles.”*
- Girl – Büşra: *“We were living in Homs, Syria. I am 10 years old. Father’s was martyred. I am a student at 4th class. We were 3 siblings. We’re come to Turkey because of the war.”*
- Girl – Dima: *“I am 15 years old. We are 5 siblings. I attend the 9th class. We were living in Latakia, Syria. My father sent us to Turkey since our lives were not safe in the war.”*
- Girl – Diyana: *“I am Diyana Şihail, I am 13 years old. We are 4 brothers/sisters. I attend the 7th class. My father was martyred in the war. We were living Homs, Syria. We’ve come to Turkey because of the war.”*
- Girl – Esma: *“We were living in Homs, Syria. My father was martyred. We are 3 siblings. We’ve come to Turkey because of the war.”*
- Girl – Fatma: *“I am Fatma I am 15 years old. We were living in Latakia, Syria. I am a student at 9th class. We’ve come to Turkey because of the war in Syria.”*
- Girl – Hala: *“I was living in Cirsusuğul, Syria. We are 3 brothers / sisters. I’ve been living at Tekel Camp, Altınözü for 4 years. I’d like to go back to my country if the war ends in Syria. I love Turkey, but I miss living at home and I want to do that.”*
- Boy – Haşim: *“My name is Haşim I am 13 years old. We are 3 brothers and 1 sister. There was a violent war when we were in Syria. Airplanes were bombing continuously. My sister was crying so much. We were scared so we came here. Finally we are safe.”*

- Girl – Kinana: *“I am Kinana, I am 14 years old. I attend to the 7th class. Father was martyred in the war. We were living in Homs, Syria. We are 5 brothers / sisters. We’ve come to Turkey because of the war.”*
- Girl – Mahha: *“I am 14 years old. I am a student at 9th class. We were living in Latakia, Syria. We’ve come to Turkey because of the war.”*
- Boy – Muhammed: *“My name is Muhammed. There a good, nice and peaceful life in Syria. One of the fathers brought us to Turkey for keeping us away from the danger, attack and war. All children like to dream. When I grow up I want to be a doctor.”*
- Boy – Nour: *“I am 16 years old. We are 4 brothers / sisters. I am a student at 8th class. My father was martyred in the war. We were living in Homs, Syria. We escaped to Turkey when the war broke out.”*
- Girl – Redah: *“I am 11 years old. We are 3 brothers / sisters. We could hear the sounds of bombs all the time and we were hiding when we were in Syria We suffered a lot while coming here. We were all in muds. We ran away from Assad’s military. My father stayed in Syria at the beginning. We love Turkey very much. They help us in any matter. I’d like to go back to my country if the situation turns to normal.”*
- Girl – Ravnak: *“I am 11 years old. We have been living at Tekel Camp, Altınözü for 4 years. I’d like to go back to my country and live at home if the war ends in Syria.”*
- Girl – Sacide: *“My father was martyred in the war. I am 16 years old. We are 5 brothers / sisters. We are living in Homs, Syria. I am a student at 10th class. We’ve come to Turkey because of the war in Syria.”*
- Girl – Şeyma: *“We are 5 brother / sisters. My father revolted against Assad. He was wanted by Assad’s soldiers. He brought us to Turkey. Then he was killed in the war.”*
- Girl – Şirin: *“I am 11 years old. My father was martyred in the war. We are 4 brothers / sisters. We were living in Latakia, Syria. I am a student at the 6th class.”*
- Girl – Yamama: *“I am 14 years old. We were living in Homs in Syria. We came to Turkey because of war. I love Turkey.”*
- Boy – Yamen: *“I am a student at the 10th class. I am 16 years old. We are 5 brothers/sisters. We were living in Latakia, Syria. We took refuge in Turkey because of the war.”*
- Boy – Yusuf: *“I am 16 years old. I am a student at the 8th class. We are 5 brothers / sisters. We were living in Latkia, Syria. We’ve come to Turkey, because of war in Syria.”*
- Girl – Semira: *“We were living in Idlib. We are here for 4,5 years. We live 12 people together here. My sister is a psychiatrist. Here’s nice but I want to go back to Syria. I want to be a surgeon.”*
- Girl – Salam: *“I came here from Damascus. We are 6 brothers / sisters and 7 people altogether. We are here for 2 years. My father, my uncle and my uncle’s daughter were martyred in the war. I’m happy to be here. I want to be an engineer.”*
- Girl – Cena: *“I arrived here from Homs, 4 years ago. My mother and father are teachers. Our daughter in law was killed. I am happy living here. I miss my country. I want to be a doctor.”*
- Girl – Maria: *“I arrived here from Latakia. We are 5 people in our family and 3 siblings. Nobody works in the family. I am happy to live here. I want to be a surgeon.”*

- Girl – Hiba: *“I arrived here from Aleppo. We are living 5 people 3 of them are brothers/sisters. Nobody works in my family. I am happy because I am safe. I want to be a surgeon.”*
- Girl – Aya: *“I am 14 years old. We were living in Idlib. We are 3 brothers / sisters. We haven’t lost anyone of the family. I want to be a doctor when I grow up. It’s nice feeling for me to live in Kilis. I miss my country.”*
- Girl – Sara Yunso: *“I am 14 years old. We were living in Idlib. We are 6 brothers/ sisters and living 8 people in a container. My parents are alive. I want to be a doctor when I grow up. It feels good to be here.”*
- Girl – Sidra: *“I came here from Idlib. We are here for 4,5 years. We are 4 brothers / sisters, total of 6 people. I am happy to live here. My uncle died in the war. I am happy to be a Syrian. I want to be a cardiologist.”*
- Girl – Esra: *“I arrived here from Latakia. We are 4 brothers / sisters. We are living 6 people here. I am happy here but I miss my country. I want to be a painter.”*
- Girl – Faten: *“We were living in Idlib. We are 4 brothers / sisters. We are living 6 people in a container. I lost my cousins in the war. We have 10 loses. I want to be a teacher when I grow up. I am happy but would be happier if I had been in Syria.”*
- Girl – Zeynep: *“I am 14 years old. We were living in Idlib. We are 6 brothers / sisters and living in a container. I lost my 3 cousins in war. I want to be an architect when I grow up. It feels good to live here.”*
- Girl – Betül: *“I am 14 years old. We were living in Idlib. We are 3 brothers / sisters. We are living 5 people in a container. I want to be an engineer when I grow up. It feels good to live in Kilis. Thanks to Turkey.”*
- Boy – Muhammed: *“I was born in Al-Shagour Village and studied in A-Shagour School, Grade Three. I could not continue school and exited my country with my family. Here I studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade four. I am still in school. Here I live a good life with my family and feel safe. I wish to return home after situations become clam there.”*
- Girl – Fatima: *“I was born in Heish Village and studied in Hassan al – Ali School. I studied to Grade Three. I could not continue study because of war. I exited with my family to Turkey and studied in Mediat Camping School Grade Four. I am still in school. I live a good safe life with my family and I hope to return to my country as soon as possible after the war ends. We thank Turkey for the good hospitality to us”.*
- Boy – Taha: *“I was born in Jisr Village and studied in Dabet School, Grade Three. I could not continue school and exited my country with my family to Turkey. Here I studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade Five. I am still in school. Here I live a good life with my family and feel safe. I wish to return to my country after situations become calm there and war ends. We thank Turkey for the good hospitality to us.”*
- Boy – Halid: *“I was born in Min Village and studied in Min School Grade One. I could not continue school and exited my country with my family to Turkey. Here I studied in Mediat Comping School Grade One. I am still in school. Here I live a good life with my family and feel safe. I wish to return to my country after situations become calm there and the war ends.”*

- Boy – Mahmud: *“I was born in Safouhon Village and studied in Safouhan School grade three. I could not continue school and exited my country with my family to Turkey. Here I studied in Mediat Camping School Grade Three. I am still in school. Here I live a good life with my brother. I wish to return home after situations become calm there and war ends. My brother and uncle paternal are martyred thanks Turkey for the good hospitality to us”.*
- Boy – Abdulrezzak: *“I was born in Kafr Obad Village and studied in Martyr Ahmed Meflaj School, Grade Three. I could not continue school and exited my country with my family to Turkey. Here I studied in Mediat Camping school, Grade Four, Five and Six. I am still in school. Here I live a good life with my family and feel safe. I wish to return to my esteemed homeland after situations become calm there and war ends. Three of our relatives were martyrs during the war in a massacre.”*
- Boy – İbrahim: *“I was born in Ain Al-Hamra Village and studied in Jin Naqra Village School, Grade Three. I could not continue school and exited my country with my family. Here I studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade Three. I am still in school. Here I live a good life with my family and feel safe. I wish to return to my country after situations become calm there, as Syria is the World Jasmine.”*
- Boy – Ramazan: *“I was born in Tamrina Village and studied in Al-Madina School, Grade Two. I could not continue school and exited my country with my family to Turkey. Here I studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade Four. I am still in school. Here I live a good life with my family and feel safe. I wish to return to my country after situations become calm there and the war is over.”*
- Boy – İsmail: *“I was born in Maghous Village and studied in Maghous School from Grade One. I could not complete study and exited my country with my family to Turkey. Here I studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade Four. I am still in school and here I live a good life with my family and feel hope. I wish to return home after situations there become calm and war ends. My brother and uncle paternal are martyrs.”*
- Boy – Sara: *“I arrived here from Idlip. We are 6 brothers / sisters and living 7 people. My father died in the war. I’m very happy to live in Kilis but I want to go back to my country. I want to be a pediatrician.”*
- Girl – Emel: *“I was born in Edleb Governorate, Hesh Village in 2006. I studied in Hussein Al-Ali School, where I studied Grade One. I could not continue study. I came Turkey because of war. I exited with my family to Turkey. Here I study in Mediat Camping School, Grade One. I am still in school and I live a good safe life with my family. I wish to return to my country as soon as possible after the war is over.”*
- Girl – Randa: *“I was born in Ebtita Village and studied in Ebtita School, Grade One, Two and Three. I could not continue studying because of the war and exited with my family to Turkey. I studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade Four, Five and Six. I am still in school. Here I live a good safe life with my family. I wish to return to my country as soon as possible after the war ends.”*
- Girl – Meryem: *“My name is Mariam. I was born in Kafr Zita in Hamid Hospital. I am 12 years old. I lived in Kafr Zita and studied First, Second and Third Grade in the Rural*

School. I was with my colleagues studying together. The teachers were very kind to us and the headmaster was very generous to us. Suddenly war came to our country. I exited with my family to Turkey. I studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade Six. I am still in school. Here I live a good safe life with my family and I wish to return to my country as soon as possible after the war finishes."

- Girl – Hatice: *"I was born in the city of Edleb and studied in Ghaleb Shahat, Grade One. The class continued but I could not continue study because of war. I escaped with my family to Turkey and studied in Mediat Camping School, Grade three. I am still in school and living a good safe life with my family. I wish I go back to my home country in the nearest time possible after the war ends."*
- Girl – Hayriye: *"I was born in Eblin Village and studied in Eblin School, Grade Three. I could not continue study because of the war and exited with my family to Turkey. I studied in Mediat School, Grade Six. I like to study and I like teachers and the Islamic Education teacher. I am still in school. I live a good and safe life with my family and I wish to return to my country as soon as possible after the war is over."*

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